

Research Trends on Bacterial Blight: A Scientometric study

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Abstract

In the present study we analysed the research publications on bacterial blight research indexed in the Web of Science for the period 1989 to 2021. Found that total 4748 research publications were published in the study period with Annual Growth Rate 1.16%. A linear growth trend is observed. The value of Relative Growth Rate (RGR) decreased from 0.97 in the year 1990 to 0.07 in the year 2017, with average Relative Growth Rate of 0.18. The values of doubling Time (Dt.) of publications increased over period from 0.80 in the year 1989 to 8.31 during 2020, with highest doubling time recorded in the year 2017 with 9.37. Collaboration Index 3.05 is observed for the study period. Total 14,187 authors contributed on bacterial blight research, most of the contributors are from USA, China and India. Wang, SP tops with 69 publications with highest h-index 35, He received total 4660 citations for his publications with 67.54 ACPP. The bacterial blight research publications spread over total 643 journals. The leading journals preferred by the scientists were Phytopathology with 248 (5.22%) publications. The Molecular Plant-Microbe Interactions journal tops in the citations received that is total 6209 citations with 52.62 ACPP and h-index is 48. One article is published in Nature Reviews Microbiology which was having highest 2 years impact factor 78.297. Among 3100 institutions Huazhong Agricultural University, China tops in terms of publications with 203 (6.55 %). Among 111 countries USA tops with 2754 (58 %) received 44,928 total citations.

Keyword: Scientometrics, Bacterial Blight; plant diseases; bibliometric; publication trend.

Introduction

Agriculture is backbone of any country as its offers the food needs of the growing population across the world. Farming community is facing many problems mainly diseases in plants cause loss in the crop yield. The main cause of plants diseases are bacteria, viruses and fungi. Diseases with plants harmful to the crop production or yields, the loss in the yield further affects the seed quality and contamination of the grain (Skelsey & Newton, 2015). Farming community facing many problems with plant diseases, scientists across the world involved in the prevent and support such type of plant diseases to overcome and get good crop yield. Blight is a specific symptom affecting plants in response to infection by pathogenic organism. Blight is a rapid and complete chlorosis, browning, this death of plant tissues such as leaves, branches, twigs or floral organs (Agrios, 2005).

Using bibliometrics and scientometrics analysis, we can further understand the status and trends of research on Bacterial Blight. In recent years Scientometrics has been broadly used as a quantitative analysis method in many scientific research fields (Rao, 1998). The measurement of bibliographic information offers the promise of providing a theory that will resolve many practical problems. It is claimed that patterns of author productivity, literature growth rates and related statistical distributions can be used to evaluate authors, to assess disciplines and to manage collections (Sangam, 2015; Keshava et.al., 2010; Sangam, 2010). In the present paper an attempt has been made to study the publication trends in Bacterial Blight research during 1989 to 2021.

Objectives

The specific objectives of this study are:

- To identify the publication trend in the field of Bacterial Blight research;
- To identify the prolific contributors in the field of Bacterial Blight research;
- To identify the most preferred journals to communicate their research output;
- To find out the collaboration patterns of the authors, institutions, and country

Data and methodology

The study aims at analysing the distribution and research trend on bacterial blight. For the present study, the data has been collected from Web of Science core collection database, records pertaining to the field Bacterial Blight research publications for the period 1989 to 2021 in the month of February 2022. A total of 4,748 publications were retrieved in plain text format and analysed with bibliometric methods quantitatively. RStudio software is used for statistical analysis and VOSviewer software is used for graphical visualisation of collaboration network

Data analysis and Discussion

Publication trend

Figure 1 shows that, the year wise growth of publications and mean total citations per article. Total 14187 authors have contributed total 4748 publications and spread over 643 journals on bacterial blight research during the year 1989 to 2021 with Annual Growth Rate 1.16%. A linear growth trend is observed over study period. These total publications are cited total 1,29,926 times among 99,392 times cited without self-citations.

Figure 1 Year wise growth of publications and mean total citations per article

The Relative Growth Rate (RGR) increases in the number of publications per unit of time. This definition was derived from the description of relative growth rates in the study of growth analysis of individual plants and is effectively applied in the files of botany (Hunt, 1982) (Hoffman & Poorter, 2002; Ganjihah & Keshava, 2015). Doubling time (Dt.) is defined as the time to be taken to double in the size or value and exists a direct equivalence between the relative growth rate and the doubling time (Ganjihal & Keshava, 2015).

It is observed that the value of Relative Growth Rate (RGR) (Sangam, Liming, & Ganjihah, 2010) decreased from 0.97 in the year 1990 to 0.07 in the year 2017 with average Relative Growth Rate of 0.18. The values of doubling Time (Dt.) of publications increased over period from 0.80 in the year 1989 to 8.31 during 2020, with highest doubling time recorded in the year 2017 with 9.37 (Keshava, Ganjihah, & Gowda, 2008). CAGR, or compound annual growth rate, is a method to calculate the growth rate for overall period is observed 2.12 during study period.

Most prolific Contributors

The study reveals that, total 132 publications are with single-authored documents and rest of the publications are multi authored documents with Collaboration Index 3.05. Table 1 shows the top 10 most prolific authors, total 14,187 authors published 4,748 publications in the field of

bacterial blight research during 1989 to 2021 as reflected in Web of Science database. The data reveals that the most of the contributors are from USA, China and India. Wang, SP tops with 69 publications with highest h-index 35 (Keshava, Hiremath, Lamani, & Ganjihal, 2009). He received total 4660 citations for his publications with 67.54 average citations per publications. Followed by Verdier V. stands 2nd position with 67 publications, h-index 28, he received total 2806 citations with 41.88 ACPP. Leach, JE stands 3rd with 60 publications, h-index 32 and received total 3412 citations with 56.87 ACPP. Li, XH tops 4th with 54 publications, h-index 29 and received total 3848 citations with 71.26 average citations per publications (Keshava, AN, Ganjihal, & H, 2010). Figure 2 depicts top authors contributions over study period and figure 3 shows the collaboration network among authors.

Table 1. Top 10 contributors in the field of Bacterial Blight research

Sl.No.	Name of Author	Affiliation	Publications	AF	h-index	TC	ACPP
1	Wang SP	Huazhong Agricultural University, Wuhan, China	69	13.10	35	4660	67.54
2	Verdier V	Research Institute for Sustainable Development, France	67	12.08	28	2806	41.88
3	Leach JE	Kansas State University, Manhattan	60	10.21	32	3412	56.87
4	Li XH	Zhejiang University, Hangzhou, China	54	8.61	29	3848	71.26
5	Szurek B	Martin Luther University of Halle-Wittenberg, Germany	47	6.29	23	1840	39.15
6	Wang L	Chinese Academy of Sciences, Beijing, China	38	5.96	19	2369	62.34
7	Laha GS	ICAR-Indian Institute of Rice Research, Hyderabad, India	37	3.15	13	605	16.35
8	Sonti RV	CSIR–Centre For Cellular And Molecular Biology (CCMB), Hyderabad, India	36	10.51	21	1615	48.75
9	Mew TW	The International Rice Research Institute (IRRI), Philippines	36	9.12	19	1755	25.97
10	Singh AK	Indian Institute of Technology Guwahati, Guwahati, Assam, India	36	4.05	15	935	44.86

AF- Articles Fractionalized; TC-Total Citations; ACPP- Average citations per publications

Figure 2 Top authors' production over time

Figure 3 Authors collaboration Network

Top Prolific Journals for communication of research output

The bacterial blight research publications spread over total 643 journals. The leading journals preferred by the scientists were Phytopathology published by The American Phytopathological Society, USA with 248 (5.22%) publications, followed by Plant Disease published The American Phytopathological Society, USA with 229 (4.82%) , Molecular Plant-Microbe Interactions published by The American Phytopathological Society in cooperation with the International Society for Molecular Plant-Microbe Interactions, USA with 118 (2.49%), European Journal of Plant Pathology published by Springer Nature and European Foundation for Plant Pathology, The Netherlands with 99 (2.09%). The table 2 provides detailed insight on the

top 20 journals which have published 50 or more number of publications in the field of Bacterial Blight research during the study period (Ganjihal, Ganjihal, & Kwati, 2023).

The Molecular Plant-Microbe Interactions journal tops in the citations received that is total 6209 citations with 52.62 average citations per publications and h-index 48. Followed by Phytopathology with h-index 45 and total 5978 citations received with 24.10 ACPP.

Table 2 Top 20 most productive journals

Rank	Journal Name	Publisher	TP	%	TC	ACPP	h-index	IF 2021
1	Phytopathology	The American Phytopathological Society, USA	248	5.22	5978	24.10	45	4.010
2	Plant Disease	The American Phytopathological Society, USA	229	4.82	3726	16.27	31	4.614
3	Molecular Plant-Microbe Interactions	The American Phytopathological Society / the International Society for Molecular Plant-Microbe Interactions, USA	118	2.49	6209	52.62	48	3.422
4	European Journal of Plant Pathology	Springer Nature and European Foundation for Plant Pathology, The Netherlands	99	2.09	1758	17.76	21	2.224
5	Frontiers in Plant Science	Frontiers Media SA, Switzerland	94	1.98	1918	20.40	26	6.627
6	Euphytica	Springer Nature	89	1.87	2952	33.17	23	2.185
7	Plant Pathology	Wiley-Blackwell	87	1.83	1550	17.82	22	2.772
7	PLoS One	Public Library of Science	87	1.83	2288	26.30	26	3.752
8	Journal of Plant Pathology	Springer Nature	83	1.75	545	6.57	14	2.643
8	Theoretical and Applied Genetics	Springer Nature	83	1.75	4975	59.94	43	5.574
9	Molecular Plant Pathology	Wiley-Blackwell	80	1.68	3223	40.29	25	5.52
10	Journal of Phytopathology	Wiley-Blackwell	69	1.45	707	10.25	15	1.826
11	Scientific Reports	Springer Nature	68	1.43	1098	16.15	21	4.996
12	Journal of Plant Registrations	Wiley-Blackwell	66	1.39	289	4.38	8	0.902
13	Crop Science	Wiley-Blackwell	64	1.35	2349	36.70	26	2.763
14	Applied And Environmental Microbiology	American Society for Microbiology	59	1.24	3694	62.61	28	5.005
15	Frontiers in Microbiology	Frontiers Media S.A.	57	1.20	1037	18.19	18	6.064
16	Molecular Breeding	Springer Nature	56	1.18	1706	30.46	25	3.297
17	Rice	Springer Nature	54	1.14	1197	22.17	18	5.638
18	Plant Pathology Journal	Korean Society of Plant Pathology	52	1.10	402	7.73	12	2.321
19	Physiological and Molecular Plant Pathology	Elsevier	51	1.07	1329	26.06	19	2.741

20	Biological Control	Elsevier	48	1.01	1157	24.10	20	3.857
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TP- Total Publications; TC- Total citations; ACP- Average Citations per publication; IF-Clarivate Analytics Journal Citation Report Impact Factor 2021

Figure 4 depicts the rank wise journals according to the JCR impact factor 2021. One article is published in Nature Reviews Microbiology which was having highest 2 years impact factor 78.297. Followed by 4 articles published in Nature Biotechnology having 2 years impact factor 68.164 and one article published in Nature Reviews Genetics IF 59.581. 5 publications in Nature IF 69.504 and 6 publications in Science IF 63.714. Total 100 articles published in the journals having impact factor between 10 to 20. Total 29 articles published in the journals having impact factor between 9 to 9.99, 40 articles (IF between 8 to 8.99), 52 articles (between 7 to 7.99), 84 articles (between IF 6 to 6.99), 421 articles (between IF 5 to 5.99), 1032 articles (4 to 4.99 IF), 533 articles (3 to 3.99 IF), 652 articles (2 to 2.99 IF), 1019 articles (1 to 1.99 IF) and 765 articles published in the journals which are not having impact factor.

Even though we found good number of articles published in high impact factor journals, the comparison should not be taken as a reflection on agriculture research. Agriculture unlike Biology and Physics is a low-impact journal field. Besides much of the research in Agriculture is mainly of local relevance (Arunachalam & Umarani, 2021)

Figure 4 Number of Publications and JCR Impact Factor 2021

Top prolific Institutions

Table 3 shows the top most productive institutions on bacterial blight research. Total 3100 institutions shared 4748 publications during 1989-2021. Huazhong Agricultural University, China top in terms of publications among institutions with 203 (6.55 %), International Rice Research Institute, Philippines 2nd position with 194 (6.26 %), Nanjing Agricultural University, China with 143 (4.61 %) and Cornell University, USA & University of Florida, USA with 120 (3.87 %) publications each. From the data it shows that the institutions from USA, China, Philippines and India are the prominent in the field of bacterial blight research (Ganjihal G. A. & Keshava, 2015). Figure 5 shows the collaboration network between top prolific institutions on bacterial blight research.

Table 3 Top 20 Prolific Institutions

Sl.No.	Institution Name	Place	Articles	%
1	Huazhong Agricultural University	China	203	6.55
2	International Rice Research Institute	Philippines	194	6.26
3	Nanjing Agricultural University	China	143	4.61
4	Cornell University	USA	120	3.87
5	University of Florida	USA	120	3.87
6	University of California, Davis	USA	116	3.74
7	University of Nebraska	USA	110	3.55
8	Michigan State University	USA	96	3.10
9	Universiti Putra Malaysia	Malaysia	96	3.10
10	Guizhou University	China	84	2.71
11	Iowa State University	USA	83	2.68
12	Indian Agricultural Research Institute	India	82	2.65
13	Tamil Nadu Agricultural University	India	82	2.65
14	Oregon State University	USA	81	2.61
15	Institute of Plant Protection	China	78	2.52
16	Kansas State University	USA	76	2.45
17	Colorado State University	USA	73	2.35
18	Zhejiang University	China	68	2.19
19	University of Illinois	USA	64	2.06
20	Louisiana State University	USA	63	2.03
	Truncated: 3080 institutions contributed rest of the publications			

Figure 5 Institutional Collaboration Network

Top Countries /Region

Table 4 shows that, the top 20 countries contributed in the field of bacterial blight research. Total 111 countries contributed 4748 publications. Among 111 countries USA tops with 2754 (58 %) received 44,928 total citations with 44.70 average citations per publications.

Followed by China 2144 (45.16 %) received total 19,608 citations with 21.17 ACP. India shared with 1165 (24.54 %) publications received total 8543 citations with 17.51 ACP and South Korea shared 709 (14.93 %) publications received total 3769 with 15.32 average citations per publications.

Table 4 Top 20 Countries in publications on Bacterial Blight research

Sl. No.	Country Name	Publications	%	Total Citations	ACPP
1	USA	2754	58.00	44928	44.70
2	China	2144	45.16	19608	21.17
3	India	1165	24.54	8543	17.51
4	South Korea	709	14.93	3769	15.32
5	Japan	536	11.29	5449	28.09
6	Germany	442	9.31	7065	43.08
7	France	426	8.97	3841	27.83
8	Brazil	394	8.30	1448	9.72
9	Canada	339	7.14	2615	20.75
10	Philippines	246	5.18	5187	74.10
11	UK	222	4.68	3362	42.56
12	Pakistan	196	4.13	491	8.18
13	Italy	161	3.39	1087	15.99
14	Colombia	157	3.31	1031	16.63
15	Spain	154	3.24	2009	28.30
16	Malaysia	151	3.18	651	15.14
17	Thailand	122	2.57	493	15.41
18	Australia	121	2.55	702	17.55
19	Switzerland	116	2.44	2438	51.87
20	Turkey	116	2.44	461	9.41
	Others	1691	35.61	-	-

ACPP- Average citations per publications

The figure 6 depicts the country collaboration map of countries with at least 30 papers co-authored by the researchers, in the co-authorship map, the size of circles demonstrates the magnitude of the publication number and line thickness of the co-authorship rate.

Figure 6 Country collaboration Network

Mapping of Key word Co-occurrence

Total 7745 author's keywords and 6970 keywords plus occurred across 4748 publications. The keyword co-occurrence map visualizes (figure 7) the 20 highly used author keywords which have appeared at least 162 times in all documents included. Figure 8 depicts the mapping of key word Co-occurrence.

Figure 7 Word occurrences

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